

Land Suitability Evaluation for Maize Production Among the Soils of Hyuku in Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Suitability evaluation of soils of Hyuku in Wukari Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria was carried out with the view to characterize and evaluate the soils for its suitability for maize production. Two soil units were identified based on their physical, chemical and morphological features using grid method of soil survey. Two profile pits were sunk in each unit, making a total of four pits in all. The soils were deep (80 to 115 cm), well drained with sandy loam surface textures and sandy loam to clay loam subsurface textured. The soil reaction was moderately acidic (5.65 to 6.75) with high base saturation (95.07 to 96.40 %), low organic carbon (0.13 to 0.34 %), low nitrogen (0.17 to 0.67 %), and moderate to low available phosphorus (2.77 to 5.52 ppm). The soil characteristics were matched with the requirement of maize and the overall suitability rating of the soils were obtained using limitation method. Units I and II soils were rated as moderately suitable (S₂) for maize production.

Keywords: land suitability, evaluation, maize production and soil

Introduction

Maize is one of the main staple crops grown in Nigeria. Improving yield and efficiency in resource use is vital to ensuring adequate food security and environmental sustainability. The slight increase in maize production in Nigeria has been attributed to increase in hectares devoted to its cultivation and not optimum yield of each farmland. Recent report of FAOSTAT (2012) has also shown that the cultivation of areas used for maize production (Kaduna state) have declined by about 20 % from the periods of 1991 to 2000 and 2001 to 2010. In addition, the potential yield of maize crop using the improved seedling in Nigeria is not enough compared to that of the developed countries (Oyekale, 2008). Also, very key is the improper land-use resulting to land degradation and decline in agricultural

productivity generally with maize inclusive. One of the best ways of soil conservation is the allocation of the soil to its most suitable use. Allocation of the soil/land to its best uses is referred to as Land use planning in which the characteristics of the land are compared or matched with the requirements of particular land use. Land use planning also known as land suitability ensured optimum or even maximum output and at the same time guarantees minimum damage to the land resources.

Land suitability is the fitness of a given type of land for a defined use. Land suitability assessment for agriculture is meant to evaluate the ability of a piece of land to provide optimal ecological requirement of a certain crop variety. That is, assessing the capability of land is enabling optimum crop development and maximum productivity. Thus, evaluation needs a specification of the respective crop requirement and calibrating them with the terrain and soil parameters (Dent and Young, 1981). The identified limiting factors could be managed to suit various crop requirement and improve crop productivity. This is a pre-requisite to productivity maximization in agricultural sector (Pareta and Jain, 2010). Land evaluation provides avenues for sustainable land use since land will be used according to its capability. This therefore, makes it mandatory in this study to carry out land suitability in order to ensure that the selected site is suitable and capable of sustaining long term production of maize.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study area is located in Hyuku, Wukari Local Government Area of Taraba State, North East of Nigeria. It lies between latitude 7° 51' to 7° 85'N and longitude 9° 46' to 9° 78' E, of the Greenwich meridian. The entire area is a gently undulating plain, with a mean altitude of 200m above the Sea level. The drainage systems drain northward and serve as tributaries network to the river Benue while Eastward discharge of rivulets and other smaller tributaries from Wukari town drains towards the Donga River, which is a major tributary of River Benue. The mean annual rainfall value ranges from 1000-1500mm. The onset of the raining season is usually around April, while the offset period is October. The mean maximum temperature is being experienced around April at about 40°C while the mean minimum temperature occurs between the period of December and February at about 20°C (NIMET, 2015). The study area is situated over Cretaceous sandstone popularly known as Bima-sandstone. The vegetation consists of grassland interspersed with trees and shrubs. The soils are moderately deep to deep, well-drained to poorly drained, with loamy sand to sandy loam surface over sandy clay loam to sandy clay subsurface (Peng *et al.*, 2006). Land use includes the cultivation of Maize (*Zea mays L.*), Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata L.* Walp), Groundnut (*Arachis hypogea*), Rice (*Oryza sativa*), Guinea corn (*Sorghum bicolor*), Beniseed (*Sesamum indicum*), Bambara nut (*Voadenzia subterranea*), Yam (*Dioscorea spp*), Okra (*Albemoschus esculentus*), as well as Cashew (*Anacardium occidentale*) and Mango (*Mangifera indica*) as well as Oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis*) plantations. Grassland areas support animal grazing activities.

Field and Laboratory Studies

The area was soil surveyed using the grid method. Auger point investigations were carried out at 100 m intervals along traverses cut at 100 m apart on the baseline. Based on these investigations, two soil units were identified and two profile pits were sunk in each. The

pits were described according to the guideline for soil profile description (SSS, 2014) and the samples were collected and taken to laboratory for physical and chemical analysis. The air dried, crushed and sieved ($d < 2\text{mm}$) samples were analyzed for particle size distribution (PSD), pH, organic carbon, CEC, exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, K and Na), total N, available P, and base saturation.

PSD was determined by Bouyoucos hydrometer method (Day, 1965). Soil pH was determined by electrometric methods as described by IITA (2015). Walkley and Black method as described by Nelson and Sommers (1982) was employed for organic matter content determination. Total N was determined using the modified macro-kjeldahl method as described by IITA (2015). Bray No.1 method was used for extractable P. For exchangeable bases, Ca and Mg were determined by AAS while K and Na were done by flame photometer. CEC was determined by IITA (2015) procedures while base saturation was calculated by dividing TEB by ECEC and multiplying by 100%.

Land Suitability Evaluation (LSE)

The FAO framework for soil suitability classification was used for the study, according to Sys (1985). The suitability of the soils was evaluated by a direct method where the established soil land characteristics (Sys, 1985) were cross-matched with the soil land characteristics obtained from the study. The outcome was cross-matched with the suitability class rates and agricultural uses, according to Ezeaku (2011).

Results and Discussion

Soil Morphological Characteristics

The soil morphological characteristics examined in the study area include; the soil colour, texture, structure, depth and consistence (Table 1). The soils were predominantly dark reddish brown (2.5 YR 2.5/6), reddish brown (2.5 YR 5/4) and light reddish brown (2.5 YR6/3) colours (moist) in their A and Ap horizons of all the profiles. This could be attributed to the presence of relatively high organic matter which is the main colouring agent on surface soils (Ufot, 2012). In the subsurface horizons of the profiles, the presence of light reddish brown (2.5 Y 6/4 moist) and reddish colour is an indication of complete organic matter decomposition (oxygen rich soil) and seasonal fluctuation of ground water table resulting in the reddish yellow (5YR 7/6) mottles observed. Such mottles were mainly confined to root channels because of the oxidizing effect of oxygen, which enters the channels as soon as the water table receded. The soils were deep ranging from 80 to 110 cm. They are generally well drained with sandy loam surface textures while the sub-surfaces varied from sandy loam to loam to silty clay loam to loam. The textures of these soils reflected the parent rocks from which they are formed, the rate and the nature of some weathering processes (Ahukaemere *et al.*, 2016; Idoga and Azagaku, 2005). The soil structures were well developed being moderate medium crumb to moderate medium subangular blocky at the surface while the subsurface was moderate medium subangular blocky to strong medium crumb. The structures are functions of organic matter content of the soil (Akinyemi and Vivian, 2001).

Physical and Chemical Properties of the Study Area

The physical properties of the soils of the study site are shown in Tables 2. For all the profiles, sand fraction ranged from 31.2 to 75.4% in surface and subsurface soils respectively. Similarly, silt fraction varied from 20.4 to 38.8% respectively; and a range of 4.0 to 38.0% for clay fraction at the surface and subsurface respectively were observed. The texture of the soils studied was sandy loam at the surface while subsurface horizons varied from sandy loam to clay loam.

The chemical properties of the soils are shown in Table 2. The overall results show that the soils were moderately acidic with pH ranging from 5.65 to 6.75. Organic carbon varied from 0.04 to 0.34 while that of total nitrogen varied from 0.17 to 0.75%. Available phosphorus content ranged from 2.65 to 5.52 mg kg⁻¹. The organic carbon together with total nitrogen and the phosphorus were rated low. Generally, these may be attributed to release from plant tissues, gaseous loss, surface runoffs, leaching, climatic factors, vegetation, human activities and initial soil pH. Loss of N through denitrification and volatilization may also contribute to the low level of N in the wetland (Brady and Ray, 2014). The exchangeable bases were low as a result of the nature of the underlying parent materials, intensity of weathering, leaching, low activity clay, low O.M, erosion and lateral translocation of bases. Ca was the most dominant cations with values ranging between 4.42 and 4.6 cmolkg⁻¹ in the exchange complex. This may be linked to the occurrence of exchange sites which have specific affinity to Ca (Idoga, 1985) or may be due to the fact that Ca is least easily lost from exchange site or has high displacement ability over other cation exchange reaction. The Mg values varied between 0.66 and 0.93 cmolKg⁻¹ while that of K and Na varied from 0.24 to 0.31cmolKg⁻¹ 0.76 to 0.94cmolkg⁻¹ respectively. These values confirmed the predominance of Ca over Mg, K and Na as observed by Idoga, 1985, and Ogunkunle, 1989. CEC content varied between 6.62 and 6.80 cmolkg⁻¹ and were rated low. The CEC of the soils were low to medium with values ranging between 3.75 and 8.34cmolkg⁻¹. The low CEC values may be attributed to the nature of clay minerals (kaolinite) and low organic carbon level of the soils. The percentage base saturation values were very high (95.07% to 96.69%). The high base saturation could probably have associated with the presence of weathered minerals which release nutrients into the soil and their alluvial nature (Table 2).

Suitability Rating for Maize Production

Land suitability assessment for agriculture is meant to evaluate the ability of a piece of land to provide optimal ecological requirement of a certain crop variety. That is, assessing the capability of land is enabling optimum crop development and maximum productivity. Thus, evaluation needs a specification of the respective crop requirement and calibrating them with the terrain and soil parameters (Dent and Young, 1981). The identified limiting factors could be managed to suit various crop requirement and improve crop productivity. This is a pre-requisite to productivity maximization in agricultural sector (Asadu and Ezike, 2017). Land evaluation provides avenues for sustainable land use since land will be used according to its capability. This therefore, makes it mandatory to carry out land suitability in order to ensure that the selected site is suitable and capable of sustaining long term production of crops with maize inclusive.

Table 1. Morphological Properties of the Soils of Hyuku

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Color (moist)	Mottles	Mottle detail	Texture	Structure	Consistence	Inclusion	Boundary
Unit 1 Profile 1:									
Ap	0-18	2.5YR ^{2.5} / ₃ DRB	-	-	SL	2MCR	SSW	Few Medium Roots	ds
AB t ₁	18-30	2.5YR ⁵ / ₄ RB	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Few Fine Roots	ds
B t ₂	30-45	2.5YR ⁶ / ₄ LRB	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Few Fine Roots	ds
Bt ₃	45-80	2.5YR ⁵ / ₆ R	-	-	CL	2MSBK	VSW	Few Fine Roots/hard coherent rock at 80cm	-
Unit 1 Profile 2:									
Ap	0-21	10YR4/6DYD	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Many coarse roots	ds
AB t ₁	21-34	5YR6/6RY	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Many coarse roots	ds
B t ₂	34-40	7.5YR6/4LB	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Common medium roots	gs
Bt ₃	40-90	2.5YR5/2GB	-	-	CL	3CCR	VSW	Few medium roots	-
Unit 2 Profile 1:									
Ap	0-22	2.5YR 3/3DRB	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Medium Common Roots	ds
AB t ₁	22-37	2.5YR 6/3LRB	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Few fine roots	ds
Bt ₂	37-55	2.5YR 6/3LRB	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Few fine roots	gs
Bt ₃	55-89	2.5YR 7/6LRB	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Few Fine Roots	ds
B t ₄	89-110	2.5YR 6/8LRB	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Few Fine Roots	-
Unit 2 Profile 2:									
Ap	0-20	7.5YR6/4LB	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Many medium roots	ds
AB t ₁	20-38	5YR6/6RY	5YR 7/6	M2P	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Common fine roots	ds
Bt ₂	38-60	10YR4/6DYD	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Few fine roots	ds
Bt ₃	60-90	2.5YR5/2GB	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Few fine roots	ds
B t ₄	90-115	2.5YR5/4RB	-	-	SL	2MSBK	SSW	Few fine roots	-

Mottling Details: M3P=Many coarse prominent

Texture: SL=Sandy loam, CL=Clay loam

Structure: 3CCR = Strong coarse crumb, 2MCR = Moderate medium crumb, 2MSBK = Moderate medium subangular blocky

Consistence: SSW = Slightly sticky wet, VSW = Very sticky wet, VPW = Very sticky wet, NPW = Non-sticky wet, NSW = Non-sticky wet, Npw = Non-plastic wet

Boundary: ds = diffuse smooth, gs = gradual smooth

Colour: DB=Dark brown, GB= Grayish Brown, RY= Reddish Yellow, DRB = Dark Reddish Brown, RB = Reddish Brown, DYB= Dark Yellowish Brown, LRB = Light Reddish Brown, LB = Light Brown, R = Red

Table 2. Physical and Chemical Properties of Soils of Hyuku

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Sand	Silt	Clay	Texture	pH (H ₂ O)	O.C (%)	TN (%)	AP (mgkg ⁻¹)	Ca	Mg	K	Na (cmolk ⁻¹)	TEB	EA	ECEC	BS (%)
Unit 1 Profile 1:																	
Ap	0-18	73.2	22.8	4.0	SL	6.75	0.23	0.44	2.77	4.60	0.66	0.31	0.93	6.50	0.15	6.80	95.59
AB t ₁	18-30	63.2	28.8	8.0	SL	6.66	0.15	0.45	5.52	4.57	0.68	0.28	0.84	6.37	0.17	6.70	95.07
B t ₂	30-45	61.2	28.8	10.0	SL	5.85	0.11	0.67	5.12	4.61	0.69	0.26	0.78	6.34	0.22	6.80	93.24
Bt ₃	45-80	31.2	30.8	38.0	CL	5.92	0.08	0.45	3.60	4.58	0.67	0.26	0.77	6.28	0.32	6.67	94.15
Unit 1 Profile 2:																	
Ap	0-21	75.4	20.8	3.8	SL	6.56	0.34	0.52	2.65	4.59	0.67	0.30	0.91	6.47	0.16	6.77	95.57
AB t ₁	21-34	65.4	25.4	9.2	SL	6.47	0.26	0.53	4.42	4.56	0.69	0.27	0.82	6.34	0.17	6.71	94.49
B t ₂	34-40	65.8	22.2	12.0	SL	5.66	0.22	0.75	4.30	4.60	0.70	0.25	0.76	6.31	0.22	6.76	93.34
Bt ₃	40-90	52.2	23.8	24.0	CL	5.73	0.19	0.53	4.60	4.58	0.67	0.26	0.74	6.25	0.32	6.62	94.41
Unit 2 Profile 1:																	
Ap	0-22	59.2	34.8	6.0	SL	5.85	0.11	0.45	4.92	4.54	0.81	0.28	0.82	6.45	0.16	6.78	95.13
AB t ₁	22-37	57.2	32.8	10.0	SL	5.75	0.26	0.56	5.46	4.56	0.80	0.28	0.81	6.45	0.14	6.76	95.41
Bt ₂	37-55	47.2	38.8	14.0	SL	5.70	0.15	0.34	2.81	4.54	0.81	0.28	0.79	6.42	0.17	6.70	95.82
Bt ₃	55-89	55.6	26.5	18.0	SL	5.65	0.34	0.17	3.97	4.57	0.77	0.28	0.80	6.39	0.25	6.68	95.66
B t ₄	89-110	60.6	20.4	19.0	SL	5.70	0.04	0.39	4.78	4.61	0.79	0.26	0.76	6.42	0.29	6.66	96.40
Unit 2 Profile 1:																	
Ap	0-20	60.7	34.2	5.1	SL	5.64	0.32	0.45	4.90	4.42	0.93	0.25	0.78	6.38	0.18	6.67	95.65
AB t ₁	20-38	56.8	33.0	10.2	SL	5.82	0.24	0.58	5.44	4.64	0.72	0.29	0.79	6.44	0.15	6.72	95.83
Bt ₂	38-60	52.2	34.0	13.8	SL	5.80	0.17	0.32	2.70	4.65	0.82	0.27	0.80	6.54	0.80	6.80	96.18
Bt ₃	60-90	51.5	31.5	17.0	SL	5.74	0.24	0.27	3.88	4.56	0.78	0.26	0.80	6.40	0.34	6.70	95.52
B t ₄	90-115	48.4	30.2	21.4	SL	5.62	0.13	0.28	4.80	4.52	0.88	0.24	0.79	6.43	0.33	6.65	96.69

N = Nitrogen; AP = Available phosphorus; K = Potassium; Na = Sodium; Ca = Calcium, Mg = Magnesium

The suitability rating of Hyuku soils were carried out by comparing the qualities of the soil with the requirements of maize. The chemical characteristics of the soils such as pH, OC, CEC, exchangeable bases, available P and total N (Table 2) were found to be either conducive to maize production or can be amended by individual farmers and therefore cannot be considered to be permanent limitations.

Table 3. Land Use Requirement for Maize

Land Quality and Characteristics	100-95 S1	94-85 S2	84-40 S3	39-20 N1	19-0 N2
Climate (c):					
Annual rainfall (mm)	850-1250	850-750	750-600	600-500	-
Length of dry season (days)	Mean annual	1250-1600	1600-	>1800	<90
		150-220	130-150	1800	90-110
max temp. ($^{\circ}$ C)	22-26	22-18	110-130	36-30	>36
Relative humidity (%)	42-50	50-80	18-16	-	-
			>32	-	-
			>80		-
Topography (t):					
Slope (%)	0-2	2-4	4-8	8-16	
	0-4	4-8	8-16	16-30	>30
Wetness (w):					
Flooding	F0	M0	F1	Aeric	Poor
Drainage	Good	Moderate	Poor	Poor	Drainable
Soil physical Characteristics (s):					
Texture/Structure	CL, L	SL, LS	LCS	CS, S	S
Coarse fragments (%) 0-10 cm	<3	3-15	15-35	35-55	-
Fertility (f):					
CEC (cmolkg ⁻¹ clay)	>24	16-24	<16(-)	16(+)	-
Base saturation (%)	>50	35-50	20-35	<20	-
pH	5.5-7.0	5.5-7.0	5.0-8.0	5.0-8.0	
OC (%) 0-15cm	>2	1.2-2	0.8-1.2	<0.8	-
Av. P (mgkg ⁻¹)	>22	13-22	7-13	3-7	<3
Total N (%)	>0.15	0.10-0.15	0.08-0.10	0.04-0.08	<0.08
Extr. K (cmolkg ⁻¹)	>0.5	0.3-0.5	0.2-0.3	0.1-0.2	<0.1

Key: F0=No Flooding; F1=Seasonal Flooding; CL=Clay Loam; SL=Sandy Loam; LS=Loamy Sand; SCL=Sandy Clay Loam; S=Sand.

Source: Modified from Sys (1985)

Soil depth, drainage, slope, porosity, texture, structure and soil fertility status are important physical and chemical characteristics that influence maize growth, development and yield. The climatic condition of the area (temperature and rainfall) were highly suitable (S1) and favorable for maize production as values were higher than 640 mm and little above 28 $^{\circ}$ C (FAO, 2007). The textural class was found to be highly suitable (S1) for maize cultivation across the soil units. The soils were well drained, free from flooding and were therefore highly suitable (S1) for maize production. The organic matter content and CEC

were low and so rated marginally suitable (S3) for maize cultivation. Total nitrogen was low to moderately high and therefore rated moderately suitable (S2) for maize. Generally, the aggregate suitability class of the soils suggested that they were moderately suitable (S2) for maize production (Table 3 & 4).

Table 4. Suitability Class Scores of the Profiles in the Study Area for Maize

Land Quality and Characteristics	Profile I	Profile II	Profile III	Profile IV
Climate (c):				
Annual rainfall (mm)	S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)
Length of dry season (days)			S1(100)	
Mean annual max temp. ($^{\circ}$ C)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S3(40)	S1(100)
Relative humidity (%)	S3(40)	S3(40)		S3(40)
Topography (t):				
Slope (%)	S1(100)	S1(95)	S2(85)	S2(85)
Wetness (w):				
Flooding				
Drainage	S1(100)	S1(95)	S2(85)	S3(40)
Soil physical Characteristics (s):				
Texture/Structure				
	S1(95)	S1(95)	S2(85)	S2(85)
Fertility (f):				
ECEC (cmolkg^{-1} clay)	S3(40)	S3(40)	S3(40)	S3(39)
Base saturation (%)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)
pH	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)
OC (%) 0-15cm	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)
Av. P (mgkg^{-1})	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)
Total N (%)	S1(95)	S1(95)	N1(20)	N1(20)
Extr. K (cmolkg^{-1})	S3(84)	S3(40)	S3(84)	S3(84)
Mean value	74	63	66	63
Aggregate suitability class	S2	S2	S2	S2
Limiting Characteristics	d,n	k,n	n	d,n
Aggregate suitability class scores				
100-75 = S1, 74-50 = S2, 49-25 = S3, 24-0 = N1				

Figure 2. Interaction of Particle Size Distribution (PSD) of the Soils in Unit 1

Figure 3. Interaction of Particle Size Distribution (PSD) of the Soils in Unit 2

Figure 4. Interaction of pH, OC, TN and Av. P of the Soils in Unit 1

Figure 5. Interaction of pH, OC, TN and Av. P of the Soils in Unit 2

Figure 6. Interaction of Exchangeable Cations of the Soils in Unit 1

Figure 7. Interaction of Exchangeable Cations of the Soils in Unit 2

Conclusion

Selected soils of Hyuku were studied with the aim to characterize and evaluate the soils for its suitability for maize production. Two major soil units were identified in the area.

The soils were deep, well drained and had sandy loam to clay loam texture. They were generally moderately acidic in reaction with pH values ranged between 5.65 and 6.75. This pH range is safe for any sustainable maize production. They also have high base saturation, low value of available P, organic carbon, total nitrogen, and exchangeable cations meaning that they have high potentials to respond positively to any addition/application of fertilizer be it organic or inorganic. Based on the physical and chemical properties of the soils, they were rated as moderately suitable (S2) for maize production.

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